

Democratic Backsliding and its Differential Effects on Gender Justice Efforts: Lessons from Jordan

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Gender and politics scholars have demonstrated how movements and institutions aimed at improving the status of women are among the first targets of both authoritarian and democratic backsliders (Chenoweth and Marks 2022; Weldon 2024). And given the close relationship between democracy and feminism (Forester, et al. 2022), it is not surprising to see assaults on democracy and women's rights happening in tandem. Nonetheless, like other political phenomena, we should not expect democratic erosion to have a universal effect across different outcomes – variation explains variation.

As scholars of public policy have long argued, different types of issues involve different sorts of politics (Hall 1993; Lowi 1964). Gender and politics scholars have refined this approach, demonstrating the theoretical and empirical value of disaggregating women's rights to understand why advancements are made in some areas and not others (Gelb and Palley 1982; Htun and Weldon 2018). Thus, rather than starting from an *a priori* assumption that *all* women's rights and institutions will be affected by democratic backsliding in the same way and at the same time, there is a need to distinguish between different kinds of women's rights and gender justice efforts to better understand their relationship to anti-

democratic developments.

In my own research, I have started investigating how antidemocratic shifts have differential effects on gender equality machinery (GEMs) – the formal, state sponsored institutions aimed at elevating the status of women, sometimes referred to as “state feminism” – and autonomous feminist movements in Jordan. On the surface, both GEMs and feminist movements tackle gender inequality, but their relationships with the state are decidedly different. GEMs in Jordan are a form of governmental non-governmental organizations and, as such, they are connected to the government and represent the state's official efforts for advancing the status of women. In contrast, autonomous feminist movements, by definition, are movements that are independent from the state (and male-dominated organizations) (see Forester, et al. 2022).

Like other Middle Eastern states, the Jordanian regime has used its GEMs, like the Jordanian National Commission of Women (JNCW), instrumentally, to signal its democratic commitments and credentials to the international community through gender equality efforts (see Tripp 2019; Forester 2024a). Meanwhile, and in line with indications of “deliberalization” in Jordan (Lucas

2003), civil society space continues to shrink (Abu Rish 2017; Sander 2023; Schwedler 2022). In practice, this means that feminist advocates and policy practitioners have censored themselves, pursued less radical campaigns, and generally “toned down [their] work” (Forester 2024b, 12; see also Sander 2023). Jordan is thus supporting some institutions that promote women’s rights while simultaneously undermining the capacity of the broader women’s movement to engage in contentious forms of protest and political engagement. This suggests that, even though GEMs *can* be vectors of democracy (Forester and Mazur 2024; McBride and Mazur 2013), GEMs can also be used in service of the state.

For instance, in conjunction with the National Council for Family Affairs, the JNCW advocated for Jordan’s violence against women law, the Family Protection Act. After adopting the law, the regime received praise from the international community for supporting women’s human rights. Meanwhile, however, the state restricted the actions of independent feminist organizations that were advocating for the reform of Personal Status Laws. This prompts new questions: how closely can GEMs work with autonomous feminist organizations that have faced greater backlash from the state? How far can GEMs go in advocating for taboo or contentious issues before they too become targets of the state? And thinking comparatively, why do some backsliders target both GEMs and broader feminist movements in tandem while others do not? While Htun and Weldon (2018) show that *policy* domains like violence against women and family law are animated by different logics of gender justice, I am suggesting here that we also need to precisely articulate how state sponsored gender equality institutions and initiatives interact with autonomous feminism and the struggle to

deepen democracy and enliven civil society.

What does this discussion of GEMs and feminist movements teach us about the value of using a gender lens to understand democratic backsliding? I contend that analytically tracing how a state engages with GEMs and autonomous feminist mobilization can reveal patterns of democratic repression in authoritarian regimes and illiberal democracies. It suggests that we should similarly disaggregate “civil rights” in our analyses to understand which rights, at which moment, and in which context are threatened by the democratic rollbacks.♦

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